

CHARACTERISTICS OF THE APPEARANCE OF GENDER IDENTIFICATION IN ADOLESCENT CAREGIVERS IN SOS CHILDREN'S NEIGHBORHOODS

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Abstract. *This article talks about the possibilities of forming characteristics of the manifestation of gender identity in children of adolescent age in children's neighborhoods.*

Keywords: *global processes, social spiritual and moral values, social orphans, Gender identity, children left without parental care, child brought up in a family, integration, Gender identity.*

Introduction

Today, 200 children are constantly being educated in SOS Children's neighborhoods of Uzbekistan. One of the important tasks of this organization is to provide social and psychological support to children who are left without the care of their parents and fall into difficult life conditions. should be done. Because such children have grown up with not only physiological but also psychological trauma due to being deprived of their family and their parents. To adapt them to social life, develop recommendations for the families that will receive them in the future, and help them find their place in life, psychological analysis and study of their emotional state are necessary. important.

The global processes taking place on a global scale are causing the deterioration of not only economic and financial but also social, spiritual, and moral values. Such transformations taking place in society have profound consequences in the lives of orphans and social orphans. According to the data, "the world's population is more than 7.6 billion, 2.2 billion of them are children, and 2.7 million children are being educated in institutional institutions, not in the bosom of their families. On average, 10-20% of them are real orphans, while the absolute blind (80-90%) are social orphans.

The main part

The development of gender identity begins at birth. A particularly important age period for personality formation is adolescence and young adulthood. At these age stages, the process of forming moral and ethical beliefs is of the greatest importance. Interests, affiliations, and value systems change during adolescence; the areas of interpersonal communication and career choice remain a priority; changes in forms of identification are particularly important. The formation of the adolescent's gender identity is based on the reproduction of the dominant gender culture as a basis for the socialization of the individual. In recent years, the problem of personal development in organizations of orphans and children without parental care has become more and more relevant. The results of the study show a unique picture of the personal development of a child living in an organization for orphans and children left without parental care, and his characteristics that differ from a child brought up in a family. In recent years, the problem of personal development in organizations of orphans and children without parental care has become more and more relevant.

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Literature analysis

According to E. Erikson's epigenetic theory, during adolescence, a person finds himself in a state of personal internal conflict. and has the task of increasing. , daughter, student, etc.) and integrate them into a personal person based on this knowledge. E. Erikson emphasizes the psychosocial nature of ego identity, paying attention to conflicts between psychosocial structures, in particular, identity conflict and role confusion. According to the concept of E.L. According to Soldatova, ego-identity is a deep personal structure that performs the functions of regulation, control, and evaluation to maintain the identity, continuity, and integrated personality of adults.

The role of the mother in the formation of gender identity. The necessary conditions for the symbiotic interaction between the mother and the child are set during prenatal development and lead to the early formation of the mother's parental position about the father's parental position, O.A. Karabanova, A.G. Yetakchilar, I.G. Malkina-Pykh. Yu. Shilov, L.B. Schneider, E.G. Eydemiller and others.). Mothers, compared to fathers, are less differentiated towards children of different sexes, are more gentle and tolerant towards their sons, and allow them to show aggression towards parents and other children more than girls. Mothers prefer indirect, psychological influence on children, while fathers focus on normative interaction. The characteristic features of girls' identification with their mothers are the long time and the depth of the identification process. An emotional, trusting relationship with her mother is important for the formation of a girl's personality.

The role of the father in the formation of gender identity. From the first moments of the life of babies, fathers have a different relationship with them than mothers.

A father's social expectations leave an imprint on his subsequent interactions with the baby. If the baby is a boy, the father anticipates that the son may share his interests in the future; he hopes to repeat with his son the important experiences he had in his relationship with his own father or to compensate for what he lacked in his relationship with his father. If the baby is a girl, the father may hope that she will be beautiful and attract many admirers.

The traditional role of the father is the bearer of social norms and requirements for the child, an example of behavioral norms. According to R. Parke and E. Fromm, if the father leaves the family before the son is five years old, the son often becomes dependent on his peers, a son in a complete family He is less self-confident than a child. A growing boy becomes more and more aware of his masculinity and searches for his father to find out who he is.

In families without a father, male characteristics appear more slowly in boys. Fatherless boys are more dependent and aggressive than boys from intact families. It is more difficult for them to adopt male gender roles, so they often show rudeness aggression, and hypertrophy of their masculinity. The absence of the father has a strong influence on the gender-role orientation of children under the age of four; and older age. A boy's identity depends on the mother's relationship with the father, the child's age, and the availability of other adults to replace the father's absence.

The formation of the image of the father is influenced by the mother in conditions of little communication with him, she helps the child to create the image of the absent father. The child's conscious and unconscious attitude towards the role of his father, even if he is physically absent

(dead, does not live in the family), shapes the child's perception of his father and his attitude towards him.

Thus, the formation of gender identity is determined by various factors: the social status of development, social environment, upbringing, the presence of siblings, the influence of the environment, etc.

Adolescent personality is an identity [19]. According to Yu.M. Nabiul-line, the child's unsatisfied need to communicate with the same-sex parent leads to identification with the other-sex parent. During further development, the child's initial female identification changes to male [150]. In the context of organizations for orphans and children left without parental care, children are surrounded by women (pedagogues, doctors, teachers), as a result of which the boy builds his gender identity based on contradictions, or. the desire not to be like girls.

For girls, defining gender roles in orphan and orphan organizations is a continuous and less conflictual process.

According to the research results, A.L. Kozlova and N.V. According to Polyashova, children raised in organizations for orphans and children left without parental care are similar to children raised in families in the cognitive and emotional components of gender identity, but at the behavioral level, behavior specific to their gender is observed only in girls.

Summary

The following general conclusions were drawn from the above:

1. Emotions are a mental reflection of their vital meaning in the form of a direct, objective experience due to the connection between the objective characteristics of events and situations with the subject's needs. Real emotion as a psychological process cannot be distinguished from a person's long-term emotional state with the experience of the current situation or reaction to it. A state of mind is a product of psychological processes and is used for a conditional distribution in the psychology of a person at a given time.

2. As an alternative to orphanages, SOS Children's Villages, which has more than half a century of experience in the lives of orphaned children, will review the basic principles and standards of SOS Villages. Unlike children in orphanages, SOS children have a normal level of anxiety and have a deep emotional connection with their SOS mother.

3. Emotional states manifested in children of SOS children's centers, psychological states, self-awareness, activity, opposite evaluations of mood with a continuous sequence of intermediate value, levels of psychological properties such as anxiety, frustration, aggressiveness, and rigidity, and depressive the condition is aimed at the differential diagnosis of conditions close to the depressive condition.

Based on the experiences of our research, we can make the following recommendations for the prevention and rehabilitation of negative emotions in SOS children's centers:

1. In any case, it is recommended to be able to maintain mental balance, and emotional stability, to accept all sorts of defects without getting into aggression, and to look for solutions together with specialists.

2. Forming the ability of students to always maintain a positive mood, to develop the ability to accept and fight against their circumstances; acquiring cognitive knowledge about aggressive characters and using them correctly, forming a positive relationship with SOS "mother", "aunt", "social worker" and other people around without giving in to negative emotions, using their help

and trying to re-adapt to the social environment, it is recommended to use empirical results in research work to follow a healthy lifestyle and carry out rehabilitation activities.

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